

The Effect of Economic Corruption and Political Instability on Nigerian Economy

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Abstract

Corruption and instability has been a great challenge in Nigeria and have affected virtually all facets of the economy and the political system. The study focused on the effect of economic corruption and political instability in Nigeria on real economy in Nigeria. The study used secondary data from 1997 to 2022 and sourced the data from the Central Bank of Nigeria and World Development indicators of various editions. The ordinary Least Square estimator and Granger causality test were used to achieve the stated objectives of the study. The results revealed that economic and political instability exert adverse effects on the aggregate economy real output in Nigeria, while other control variables did align with their a priori expectation because of the interaction of economic and political instability in the system. The causality test showed that economic corruption has the predictive power to cause changes in the political system. Therefore, it was recommended that the government should consciously reduce corruption in the system by strengthening the institutions and political structure in the country.

Keywords: Accumulation by Dispossession. Economic Corruption, Economic output, Political Instability, Rentier Capitalism, Real Output

Introduction

The neoliberalism movement accentuated by Margaret Thatcher in the United Kingdom (UK) and Roland Reagan in the United States (US) instigated the prompting of the spread of globalization beyond the 1980s to the global South with the transfer of overconcentrated accumulated capital seeking diffusion to penetrate fragile economies where unexploited opportunities can be converted into profit maximization (Standing, 2016). This was not a charitable venture; it was typically engineering of spatial fix to recalibrate local economies that needed capital for expansion to stimulate economic growth. The attraction of foreign capital to the local economy (like Nigeria) had required neoliberal reforms taking the shape of privatization of public assets (buy over), rollback of the state in economic organizations from enterprises and public intervention, deregulation of financial and social service sectors, and the liberalization of the market as the allocative institution predisposing dominance over society (Christophers, 2020; Harvey, 2020; Standing, 2016).

Critically, Nigeria is entangled in this relation of neoliberal reforms mainly from its development by invitation synchronism, and dependency posture to partially possess and extract crude oil

resources, since it lacks the technology and funding for the project. This invitation had colonial linkage taking the form of a predatory complex extending beyond mineral extraction, technology deployment, financialization, market liberalization, labour, and societal displacement (Ebohon, 2013; Falola, 2021; Falola & Heaton, 2008; Lewis, 2006).

The neoliberal economy is typically analyzed from the perspective of promoting efficiency through competition, privatization of ownership structure, control of capital, and the socialization of production, distribution, exchange, and consumption. The ownership of capital and technology of extraction tend to create hegemony in scarce resource investment and management. As the Nigerian State claims ownership of mineral resources in the country, it requires foreign capital and technology to extract and refine the resources. The capital injection and technological deployment facilitated by foreign multinational corporations in Nigeria account for more than 90% of foreign exchange earnings, and 80% of contribution to the national budget (Christophers, 2021; Ikelegbe, 2005; National Bureau of Statistics, 2022; Okonjo-Iweala, 2012; Sanghera & Satybaldieva, 2023).

Investment in the oil sector has been monopolized by Oil Multinational Corporations (OMC-Shell, Chevron, Mobil, Agip, and Total). This provides leverage as Joint Venture Partners with the Nigerian State to own and control viable scarce oil resources as part of the energy sources that are fueling the global economy. The sector is typical for its accruing rent to the Nigerian State and the OMC. This is implicated as rentier capitalism and is notorious for corruption embedded in the failure of disclosure between the Nigerian State and the OMC on the quantum of mineral resources extracted from the ground (Christophers, 2020; Rosenberg, 2017; Standing, 2016).

The environment (air, land, and water) from which the oil resources are extracted and the people who culturally inhabit these places are dispossessed of the gains derived, the capital accumulated is discreetly shared between elites with political and economic power and the OMC. The capital accumulated and asset dispossession scheme over time create exponential wealth for the elites and OMC while dialectically reproducing increasing poverty, economic inequality, and social disruption (Harvey, 2004, 2018).

Exclusive political power is used to create extractive economic institutions that undermine the democratic decision-making process, obstruct social justice, and exacerbate economic disequilibrium (Acemoglu et al., 2020; Acemoglu & Robinson, 2019, 2012). As economic opportunities become scarce through the dispossession of common assets embedded in state capture projects and increasing rentier capitalist accumulation, state and society relationship will tend to weaken to account for political instability (AichRothstein & Varraich, 2017; Aron, 2000; Asuquo, 2020; Falola & Heaton, 2008; Ikelegbe, 2013; Nelson & Prilleltensky, 2010; Oshita & Ikelegbe, 2019; Prilleltensky & Gonick, 1996; Robinson, 2023).

Rentier capitalism as a form of neoliberal reform creates a mysterious inclination that is difficult to understand in less developed economies. It generates capital for the global developed North but it is used to reproduce poverty and misery in the global South. It organically creates contradictions as a movement that is intended to create competition through expansion and innovation, but as it grows into diffused undeveloped enclaves, it becomes an instrument of alienation, targeted at asset enclosure, and a medium of extraction through coercion and corruption (Christophers, 2018; Home & Lim, 2013; Soto, 2000; Transparency International, 2020)

Corruption affects economic growth and performance in several ways. When the scale of rent drawn from the economy (returns without reproduction) exceeds the capacity of the economy to

experience growth towards other sectors, uncertainty will blossom while creating risk and disincentive to invest in the economy (Harvey, 2014).

The problems of rentier capitalism and rentier states are related to exploitation and underdevelopment and have been covered by several scholars in the realm of political economy and development studies (Christophers, 2020, 2021; Ebohon, 2013; Ifaka, 2016; Micinski, 2021; Sanghera & Satybaldieva, 2023; Shawki, 2024; Standing, 2016, 2017; Van Der Ploeg, 2011), but there exist gaps in explaining the relationship, impact and causal effects of economic corruption and political instability on real aggregate output in exploited fragmented federal states like Nigeria.

The research objective of this study is to examine the relationship that exists among economic corruption, political instability, and real aggregate output in the Nigerian Economy; and investigate the effect and causal relationship between economic corruption and political instability. The hypotheses drawn from the objectives are stated in their null form; there is no significant relationship that exists among economic corruption, political instability, and real aggregate output; there is no significant effect of economic corruption and political instability on real aggregate output; and there are no significant causal effects of economic corruption and political instability in Nigeria.

The identified independent variables are economic corruption and political instability and the dependent variable is real aggregate output in the Nigerian economy.

Literature review

Economic corruption

While underscoring the neoliberal economy policies in the United Kingdom, (Christophers, 2018, 2020; Standing, 2016) epitomized that rentierism has predominated the way capital is created without recourse to production. To properly capture how the capitalist economy operates, Harvey, (2018) noted that capital is deployed into owning means of production and hiring labour, this medium is brought together in social relations of production to produce products that are distributed and exchanged for consumption, while capital is expanded to recapitalize the economy. This cycle is repeated endlessly.

Christophers, (2020) draws our attention to a new dimension of perversion in the UK economy where the focus of the capitalists is now on ownership of rentier access for extraction of rent without concern for production. The excitement is to deploy the enclosure of common assets and convert same as a means of accumulation by dispossession (Harvey, 2004).

Standing, (2019) sees the process of forcefully capturing and converting public assets in the privatization and enclosure programmes for personal gain as a new form of corruption. The accumulation of these public assets is done in phony circumstances that rip off the public, and the trend is to create rent from these assets, ignoring production that adds value to society. The displacement of production naturally displaces labour, and creates inequality, and poverty.

The expansion of capital through asset ownership from enclosure, intellectual and private properties, land and mineral resources, technology platforms, financialization as commodification, and holding of stocks and bonds not deployed to production but are accelerated to generate rent as profit maximation contribute to the crisis of capitalism, and the source of political instability (Barrett, 2023; Bracking, 2018b; J. S. Hellman et al., 2003). These anomalies

are perpetuated by state elites who benefit from the rentier capitalist network (Barrett, 2023; Bracking, 2018a; Chindo et al., 2014; J. Hellman & Schankerman, 2000; Lewis, 2006; Smith, 2007; Standing, 2016).

The decision to transfer common resources in many cases are not disclosed to the public and in rentier States, the center of decision-making (capital cities) is spatially isolated or suspended from society. The gap in distance and communication limits accountability and promotes corruption (Campante & Do, 2012).

The dysfunctional nature of corruption is typified as extractive burden place on both political and social institutions. The weight of the extract cost from corruption reduce the ability of government to provide public service, since a portion is diverted for personal gain (Acemoglu & Robinson, 2012). Also corruption tend to erode public trust (Fukuyama, 2014, 2022) and Harvey, (2014) sees corruption as an inherent part and parcel of the capitalist structure. It is a scheme design to accumulate capital and dispossess the people from the realization of quality public service.

Corruption and political instability are deeply connected to causing distortion in preventing economic growth. Economic growth occurs when political and economic institutions are inclusive and the benefits are sharing widely (Acemoglu & Robinson, 2012). The distortion relates to accelerating the allocation of public resources to rent seeking behaviours that discourages robust investment through competition. Corruption is linked to cronic capitalism where oligarchy or narrow based elite interest are organized to survert public efficiency and disclosure in managing public resources and its distribution. Corruption is intensified through the use of state power to divert resources, reduce public service, prioritize short term gains, upsurge uncertainty, and restrict production and economic growth (Christophers, 2014; Harvey, 2014; Standing, 2016).

Political Instability

Political order is require for government to be efficient and an enabler to allow the private sector to thrive in building a viable and sustainable economy. The primary condition for order, which predisposes stability, are a strong state institution (bureaucracy), rule of law that protect private property and assure political accountability (Fukuyama, 2014). Political decay, a condition of perversion in the misuse and abuse of public institutions can create discontent, reduce public trust and generate social tension leading to political instability (Aron, 2000; Fukuyama, 2014, 2022).

When societal resources, opportunities, positions, and status are not equally or equitably distributed, social tension is created. The fragility arisen from this exclusive institutional mechanism that violates social justice principles lend causes for group grievances, and even fractionalization of elites across race, religion, region, politics, culture, and class consciousness (Constantine, 2017; Israel & Frenkel, 2017; King, 2016; Ramzan et al., 2020).

Disadvantage groups or persons are predisposes to rebel or revolt against state institution and their functioning (Agbibo, 2013; Hedges, 2015). Corruption is often associated with the privilege use of position or assigned opportunity to seek gains at the expense of others or society at large (Ahlquist & Levi, 2013; Lewis, 2006; Noonam, 2023). Primitive accumulation deployed by capitalist and rentiers can upset public interest when politics is conjure against the interest of disadvantage groups through exploitation and dispossession (Harvey, 2018; Standing, 2019).

Political instability and economic corruption can have bidirectional effects on state capacity and economic growth. Both have negative attributes towards promoting national integration, political

order and economic growth (Falola & Heaton, 2008). The quality of elite and quality of democracy (regime type) can manifest into disproportional outcomes, both quality of elite and quality of democracy are extractive, and predatory against the interest of the common (Beetham et al., 2008; Burgis, 2015; Casas & Cozzi, 2022; Hoppe, 2007; Nitzan & Bichler, 2006).

Aggregate Output:

Capitalism and the neoliberal doctrine of freemarket, privatization in the ownership of capital, predisposes the lure for investment to derive profit maximation. Capital is value in motion and run in circular motion. Capital as value in the capitalist system requires production to take place before it can effectively turn out profit. Profit occurs through social relationship. This means capital is an initiator of the production process. Capital needs to be available to procure means of production (land, machine, assets, technology, raw material) and hiring of labour power (Das, 2017; Harvey, 2010).

The means of production are inanimate and requires the effect of human to create surplus value. The production process stimulate a social relation of production, the composite of means of production to generate surplus value. The output of production is commodified and valued as capital. It is at this point that labour is exploited as a commodity and bought at sustitence value, while the surplus is extracted by the capitalist as profit (Harvey, 2018, 2020; Ledeneva, 2017; Mavroudeas & Papadatos, 2018).

Real aggregate output is concern with the total output of production (goods and services) in an econmy for a giving period under investigation. It is therefore a parameter to evaluate the productive capacity of a nation. Real aggregate output reflects the present and deployment of labour (human capital), technology and physical capital to produce the total value of goods and services in an economy (Csontos, 2023; Dunford, 2021; Greiner & Finkec, 2015; Robinson, 2023; Smith, 2009).

Measuring aggregate output in the Nigerian economy will tend to focus on where the impact of the production capacity is derived from. The Nigerian economy is hugely dependent on the cruel oil and gas. The trajectory of the Nigerian economy between 1997 to 2022 is treated under three phases. The first phase of 1997 to 1999 indicated Nigeria military rule era where the country was under severe economic santions over its human rights abase and the crude oil production experied massive restrictive slaes that was dependent on global export and price determination. The GDP growth was sluggish with on 2% realization on the back of the oil sector while agriculture and manufacturing sectors were massively ignored.

Between 1999 and 2001, Nigeria entered into the democratic frenzy and sort for debt forgiveness that restrained Foreign Direct Investment in the country. This period experience recovery, flow of investment base on trust of democratic governance. From 2002 to 2007, Nigeria intensified neoliberal reforms through provitaization of various sector and the oil sector experience oil boom with a 7% GDP growth rate for the period. The country rebased its economy in 2014 and became the largest economy in Africa with a \$510 billion economy (Okonjo-Iweala, 2012, 2018).

Mismanagement of the economy, fall in the price of oil, and excessive borrowing starting from 2015 saw Nigeria entered its first recession in 2016. The GDP ran into a negative of -1.6, recovered to 0.8% in 2017, stabilizing to 2% up to 2020. However, the pendemic brought the second recession in 2020 with a decline and negative GDP of -1.8. The relative shock associated with global oil shock and proice fluatuation saw slow post pandemic recovery of under 3% of GDP up to 2022. Analyst of the country's economy has majorly captured the driven machiney

driving the Nigerian economy as rentier laoded with corruption and variance of political instability (Acemoglu et al., 2020; Fukuyama, 2014; Harvey, 2020; Okonjo-Iweala, 2018).

Theoretical framework

Corruption affects the performacen of the economic in several ways. It reduces both foreign and domestic investments because it distorts and increases uncertainty, and risks of investment. Corruption equally increases cost of doing business, thus, discouraging people to invest (Wei,2000). The reduction in foreign direct investment does not only reduce potential economic growth, but reduces transfer of technology that would have come with such investment.

The study adopted the extractive theory of imperialism as the theoretical framework for the study. The Extractive Theory of imperialism, which was propounded by Rosa Luxemburg in 1913 in her work "The Accumlation of Capital" refers to the relationship between state, it's agent and the economic society. The theory relate the relationship of imperialism to corruption, explotation, force, violence and coercion used ot extract resources and labour (Acemoglu & Robinson, 2012). The state agent uses the resources to the benefits of their leader. Iyanda (2012) in his work on corruption definition theories and concepts he explain that the concept of extractive theory is based on the idea of authoritarianism, the use of force and exploitation of a state's resources by rulers or their agents.

Also the proponent of extractive theory of corruption is linked to Acemoglu & Robinson, (2012) in their classic book why nations fail. They established that extractive political and economic institutions embedded in corruption limit economic growth as well as propagate inequality and wide spread poverty.

Both political and economic institutions of a country can be extractive to the extent that they exclude others from participating, contributing and benefiting from both political and economic process and outcome. Political and economic exclusion naturally produce weak institutions and reproduces economic decline, intense economic inequality, legitimacy crisis and political instability (Acemoglu et al., 2020; Acemoglu & Robinson, 2019; Morelli & Seaman, 2022).

The theory backs the study up by resisting autocratic regimes and the government's officials who use power and resources of the state to protect their individual and selfish interest at the detriment of the nation economic growth. In other words, where excessive power is concentrated absolutely in the hands of a few person, there is high tendency for corruption, abuse of power, wealth seeking and extraction of resources for personal gains.

Emperical Review:

The corruption of capitalism as an instrument of labour exploitation, following the neoliberal discontent, have been associated with political instability, especially in rentier States like Nigeria. There are concern of massive state capture, state failure, state fragility, and declining economic growth related to enthrenched corruption and political instability (Dunn, 2017; Ifaka, 2016; Kaplan, 2000; Klein, 2007).

Political instability as political decay discourage invest in business, since investors are predispose to risk aversion. The stimulation of political instability are primary driven by the nature and character of state and society relations. The predisposition of post colonial state having eatures of endemic corruption, predatory, rentier, alien, comprehensively intrusive, authoritarian regime, prebendal, hegemonical, partial and partisan state, and society that has high level of elite

fractionalization, group grievance and external intervention that disruptive the productive capacity of the economy (Asuquo, 2020; Babalola, 2019; Fadakinte, 2013; LeVan, 2014; Pritchett et al., 2013; Shawki, 2024).

The challenge of corruption and political stability has been a major disruptive element in the engaging more competent human capacity in the production process in Nigeria. There is strong evidence that nepotism and corruption has prevented more qualified persons to be engage in the development of the economy. Also the exploitation of labour as driven the available human resources and capital to migrate towards more advance economy (Babalola, 2019; Burgis, 2015; Ebohon, 2013; Fukuyama, 2018; J. S. Hellman et al., 2003; Ifaka, 2022; Ifaka & Odigie, 2021; Klein, 2007; Meredith, 2005, 2019; Ngozi Okonjo-Iweala, 2012; Okonjo-Iweala, 2018; Shawki, 2024).

Empirical review from the World Bank, International Monetary funds and several scholars have persistently linked the corruption perception index of Nigeria score to demonstrate the country's posture to its recurrent decline to economic growth. Mismanagement of the Nigeria's oil rent has link with corruption of elite and state capture. Similarly, a report by Okeke had established that 1% increase in corruption reduces the GDP of the country as is explained by loss of investment, reduced quality in service delivery, and inflated contract as much as severity of abandoned projects (Okeke, 2018).

Corruption is linked to fuelling political instability (Okeke, 2018) and this is implicated by associated rise in poverty, inequality, unemployment and continued discontentment with uncertainty that scare investors away and negatively impact economic growth. A study by Eze & Obinwugo (2019) found that the 2015 election instigated political instability that showed a reduction of GDP by 2.7%. Also political instability in the form of insurgency (Militant in the Niger Delta and Boko Haram in the North East) can create hostile environment for business to operate, drive down oil production which causes decline in productions and earning in oil rents (Okon & Efang, 2020).

Political instability reflected in regime change is associated with frequent change of state policies and investors are sceptical to operate in unstable policy environment. Babatunde & Akinyemi (2021) found out that between 2015 and 2020, a transition between President Jonathan and President Buhari regimes, policy reversal were rampant and the inconsistent drastically reduced Foreign Direct Invest.

Methodology

The study used secondary data and adopt the causal and effect research design. The data were source from various editions of Freedom House, Corruption Perception Index, World Development Indicators, Central Bank of Nigeria. The researched deployed qualitative method in analyzing the data.

Method of Data Analysis-

Model Estimation techniques

This study uses descriptive statistics and time series econometric techniques. First, the descriptive statistical analysis employed univariate and matrix correlation to describe each variable in this

study. Second, the time series econometric techniques employ Ordinary Least Square time series property. It also employed the Granger causality test to determine the causal direction between variables.

Model Specifications

In this study, the model specified are based on the objectives of economic corruption (ECC) and economic output as well as political instability (PLC) and economic output. The general functional relationship between aggregate output and corruption is given as:

$$GDP = f(CORR) \quad 1$$

Where GDP is Economic output and COR is Corruption.

The model specified for economic corruption is given as:

$$GDP = f(ECC) \quad 2$$

$$GDP = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 ECC_t + \alpha_2 INF_t + \alpha_3 MANC_t + \alpha_4 FDI_t + \alpha_5 TOP_t + \varepsilon_t \quad 3$$

Where GDP is the economic aggregate output, ECC is economic corruption, INF is inflation, MCU is manufacturing capacity utilization, FDI is Foreign Direct Investment ad TOP is trade openness.

The model specified for political instability is given as:

$$GDP = f(PLC) \quad 4$$

$$GDP = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 PLC_t + \alpha_2 INF_t + \alpha_3 MANC_t + \alpha_4 FDI_t + \alpha_5 TOP_t + \varepsilon_t \quad 5$$

Where PLC is political instability and other are already defined.

The model specified granger causality test is given as:

$$\Sigma GDP_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \Sigma ECC_{t-i} + \beta_2 \Sigma PLC_{t-i}$$

$$\Sigma ECC_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \Sigma PLC_{t-i} + \beta_2 \Sigma GDP_{t-i}$$

$$\Sigma PLC_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \Sigma ECC_{t-i} + \beta_2 \Sigma GDP_{t-i} \quad 6$$

β_0 is the constant coefficient

Data Analysis and Results Interpretation

Descriptive Analysis

The descriptive analysis described the nature of the data in terms of their central tendency and dispersion. The results are presented in Table 4.1. below

Table 1: Descriptive Analysis

	Mean	Median	Maximum	Minimum	Std. Dev.	Jarque-Bera	Probability
GDP	5.08E+13	5.26E+13	7.58E+13	2.35E+13	1.85E+13	2.561616	0.277813
ECC	20.95000	22.50000	28.00000	7.00000	6.276767	2.892057	0.235504
FDIG	1.315207	1.452078	2.900249	-0.03952	0.847627	1.227372	0.541352
MANC	48.80731	51.20000	62.04000	31.29000	9.036556	2.502902	0.286089
TOP	34.71979	36.27513	51.01630	3.030810	12.24842	5.903026	0.052261
PLC	-1.74842	-1.88293	-0.58824	-2.21112	0.424015	17.24840	0.000180

Source: Authors' computation, 2024.

The results in table 1 showed that most of the data have a closed range of central tendency. That is, mean values of GDP, ECC, FDIG, MANC, TOP and PLC gap with their median values are closed. This implies that distribution of the data is not too far from the center point. The standard deviation values of all the data are below the values of the mean and media. This is due to the range of each of the data that reveal a minimal spread of the data when the minimum and the maximum values are compared. The results indicated an obvious fact that most of the data do not exhibit high degree of variabilities. Therefore, the issue of volatility is minimal and the estimation of the model does not need any auto regressive conditional heterogenous approach. The results of the Jarque-Bera showed that GDP, ECC, FDIG and MANC are normally distributed and TOP and PLC are not. However, the number of variables that are normally distributed, which are far more than the ones that are not normally distributed, strengthen the assumption of zero mean and constant variance for the joint estimation.

The maximum value of corruption perception index used to proxy economic corruption is 28, while the minimum is 7. The ranking stated that 100 is zero corruption while a low score indicates a high level of corruption. On average, the mean score recorded a approximate value of 21. Given the mean score, maximum and minimum values, corruption in Nigeria is very prominent and very far from the perfect score of 100. The political instability is proxy by the political stability in the country and score; a negative score shows that the country is politically unstable due to high degree of corruption in the political system. Both the maximum and minimum values indicated a negative value of -0.6 and -2.2 respectively and the mean score over the period is -1.75. the score is an obvious fact that the political system in Nigeria is highly unstable and corrupt.

Correlation Analysis

The estimation of correlation analysis is necessitated to test the validation of the assumption of autocorrelation in Ordinary Least Square estimator

Table 2: Correlation Analysis

Variables	GDP	ECC	FDIG	MANC	TOP	PLC
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GDP	1.00					
ECC	-0.93	1.00				
	0.00	-----				
FDIG	-0.42	-0.15	1.00			
	0.03	0.47	-----			
MANC	0.65	0.85	0.16	1.00		
	0.00	0.00	0.43	-----		
TOP	-0.16	0.04	0.73	0.22	1.00	
	0.44	0.85	0.00	0.28	-----	
PLC	-0.70	-0.86	-0.13	-0.86	-0.30	1.00
	0.00	0.00	0.52	0.00	0.14	-----

Table 2. revealed that economic corruption (ECC) and political instability (PLC) has a very strong negative and significant correlation with economic output. This implies that the economic output reacts negatively to the outcomes of economic and political instability in Nigeria. Furthermore, other macroeconomic variables such as foreign direct investment percentage share in GDP (FDIG) and trade openness (TOP) also showed a negative correlation, however not too strong like the corruption indicators. The variants nature of the correlation results indicated that there is an absence of autocorrelation and the assumption that there is not correlation among the independent variables was not violated.

Model Estimation and Interpretation of Results

The study estimated two models namely: economic corruption model and political instability model. The results in the two models substantiated the objective of the study by examining the effect of economic corruption on economic output and political instability on the economic outcome as well.

Economic Corruption Model

Economic corruption is measured by the corruption perception index and it showed the level of which corruption has eaten into the fabric of economic activities in the system. The results estimation is reported in Table 3.

Table 3: Economic Corruption Model Estimation

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
ECC	-3.33E+12	3.19E+11	10.44211	0.0000
FDIG	-4.82E+12	1.74E+12	-2.764530	0.0116
MANC	-5.64E+11	2.19E+11	-2.571598	0.0178
TOP	2.62E+10	1.06E+11	0.245715	0.8083
C	1.40E+13	5.55E+12	2.515695	0.0201
R-squared	0.954502			
Adjusted R-squared	0.945836			
F-statistic	110.1400			
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			
Durbin-Watson stat	1.539702			

Dependent Variable: GDP

The results in Table 3 discovered that economic corruption coefficient value of -3,330 billion is negative sloped and significant at 1% level of significant. This suggest that a unit increase in economic corruption index, GDP will reduce by a naira value of ₦3,330 billion per year. By implication, corruption adversely affect the economic output and all effort to develop the economy is being thwarted by the activities of corruption in the economy.

Other control variables such as foreign direct investment percentage share in GDP and manufacturing capacity utilization showed a negative and significant coefficient of -4,820 billion and -5,640 billion respectively. The negative relationship of these variables is an indication that foreign direct investment contradicts the a priori expectation and exhibit a contraction in the system. The reason behind is the level of capital flight and profit repatriation of the multinational companies and the level of manufacturing capacity utilisation is very low. The results showed that trade openness coefficient does not have any statistical significant even though it has a positive relation. The high degree of volatility of exchange rate has not been able to allow the positive effect of trade openness to reflect on the economic output in Nigeria.

The adjusted R^2 value of 0.95 indicate that the dependent variable is being explained by the independent variables by 95%. This shows a high degree of goodness of fit on the regression line. The changes and outcome of GDP is ascribed to be explained by a high tendency of ECC, FDIG, MANC and TOP. The value of F-statistic, 110.14 is significant at 1% level and it indicate that the overall model specified is appropriate and the joint effect of the changes of the independent variables is significant to cause an effect on economic output. The Durbin Watson also tested the serial correlation assumption of OLS showed that the value of 1.54 is higher than the value if the adjusted R^2 and its value is close to 2. This implies that there is no positive serial correlation of auto correction in the model estimated.

Political instability Model

In the political instability in the country and score; a negative score shows that the country is politically unstable due to high degree of corruption in the political system. The results is presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Political instability Model Estimation

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
PLC	-2.25E+13	9.41E+12	-2.391180	0.0262
FDIG	-1.21E+13	3.41E+12	-3.545075	0.0019
MANC	5.98E+11	4.29E+11	1.394915	0.1776
TOP	4.33E+10	2.44E+11	0.177366	0.8609
C	-3.38E+12	1.15E+13	-0.294263	0.7714
R-squared	0.778558			
Adjusted R-squared	0.736378			
F-statistic	18.45821			
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000001			
Durbin-Watson stat	1.452308			

Source: Authors' computation, 2024. Dependent Variable: GDP

The results in Table 4 revealed that political instability (PLC) coefficient value of -2.250 billion is negative sloped and significant at 5% level of significant. This suggest that a unit increase in political instability index, GDP will reduce by a naira value of ₦2.250 billion per year. By mplication, corruption adversely affect the economic output and all effort to develop the economy is being disenchanted by the activities of corruption in the political system.

Foreign direct investment percentage share in GDP showed a negative and significant coefficient of -1,210 billion and manufacturing capacity utilization showed a non-significant positive value of 5,980 billion. The negative relationship of these variables is an indication that foreign direct investment contradicts the a priori expectation and exhibit a contraction in the system. The reason behind is the level of capital flight and profit repatriation of the multinational companies and the level of manufacturing capacity utilisation is very low. The results showed that trade openness coefficient does not have any statistically significant even though it has a positive relation. The high degree of volatility of exchange rate has not been able to allow the positive effect of trade openness to reflect on the economic output in Nigeria.

The adjusted R^2 value of 0.74 indicate that the dependent variable is being explained by the independent variables by 74%. This shows a high degree of goodness of fit on the regression line. The changes and outcome of GDP is ascribed to be explained by a high tendency of ECC, FDIG, MANC and TOP. The value of F-statistic, 18.45 is significant at 1% level and it indicate that the overall model specified is appropriate and the joint effect of the changes of the independent variables is significant to cause an effect on economic output. The Durbin Watson also tested the serial correlation assumption of OLS showed that the value of 1.45 is higher than the value if the adjusted R^2 and its value is close to 2. This implies that there is no positive serial correlation of auto correction in the model estimated.

Granger Causality test for Casual Relationship

The Granger causality test the casual relationship of the variables and reports whether there is bi-directional effect or not. Economic output (GDP), economic corruption (ECC) and political instability (PLC) are employed to estimate their casual relationship as related to the objectives. Pairwise Granger Causality test used 2 lag criteria and reported the F-statistic and the probability value showing the level of significance.

Table 5: Pairwise Granger Causality test

Variable interaction	obs	F-statistic	Prob. Value
ECC does not Granger Cause GDP	24	2.03438	0.1583
GDP does not Granger Cause ECC		2.27128	0.1305
PLC does not Granger Cause GDP	24	2.10044	0.1499
GDP does not Granger Cause PLC		0.01491	0.9852
PLC does not Granger Cause ECC	24	1.78146	0.1954
ECC does not Granger Cause PLC		6.82131	0.0059

Source: Authors' computation, 2024.

From the results in Table 5, none of the variables shows any bi-directional relationship of effect. However, economic corruption causes the changes in political instability. This is evident in the results where ECC does not Granger Cause PLC hypothesis is rejected and the alternative is

accepted because the probability value of 0.0059 is below the 0.05 level of significance. By implication, we can deduce that economic corruption measure in terms of corruption perception index in Nigeria has the predictive power to influence the outcome of political instability. This implies economically, that the rot and decadence in the economic practices and activities lead to the instability and malpractices in the political space. The bounty or national cake perceived to be in government can only be access by gaining political power. Therefore, this perception by political leaders can lead to political tussle and invariably, instabilise the political system.

4.2. Test of Hypotheses

The following null hypothesis formulated are in line with the research question and objectives of the study. These hypotheses have been tested in the estimated model.

i. H_0 Economic corruption has no impact on economic output in Nigeria.

The estimated results found out in Table 3. revealed that economic corruption has a significant and an adverse effect on economic output in Nigeria given the level of significance and relational direction. Therefore, reject the null hypothesis that Economic corruption has no impact on economic output in Nigeria and accept the alternative hypothesis and conclude that economic corruption has a strong negative impact on economic output in Nigeria.

ii. H_0 : Political instability has no impact on economic output in Nigeria.

The estimated results found in Table 4 showed that political instability has a significant and an adverse effect on economic output in Nigeria given the level of significance and relational direction. Therefore, reject the null hypothesis that political instability has no impact on economic growth in Nigeria and accept the alternative hypothesis and conclude that political instability has a strong negative impact on economic output in Nigeria.

iii. H_0 : There is no significant causal relationship between economic corruption and political instability in Nigeria.

The results in Table 5 found out that economic corruption causes the changes in political instability and have the predictive power to influence the outcome of political instability that leads to corruption in political practices in Nigeria system. Therefore, reject the null hypothesis that there is no significant causal relationship between economic corruption and political instability in Nigeria and conclude that economic corruption causes political instability and there is a causal relationship from economic corruption to political instability in Nigeria.

5. Conclusion

Corruption and political instability affect Nigerian economy in several ways. When the scale of rent drawn from the economy (returns without reproduction) exceeds the capacity of the economy to experience growth towards other sectors, uncertainty will blossom while creating risk and disincentive to invest in the economy. The study investigated the effect of economic corruption and political instability in form of political instability on the real economy in Nigeria. Secondary data was used from 1997 to 2022 and sourced the data form central Bank of Nigeria and World Development indicators of various editions. The study adopted Ordinary Least Square estimator and Granger causality test to analysed the data and achieved the stated objectives of the study. The results revealed that economic and political instability exert adverse effects on the aggregate economy real output in Nigeria, while other control variables did align with their a priori expectation because of the interaction of economic and political instablitys in the system. The causality test showed that economic corruption has the predictive power to cause the changes in

the political instability. By implication, corruption is impede economic performance of Nigeria and its has a adverse spillover on virtually every sectors of the economy in Niegria.

Therefore, it is imperatice to remove or reduce corruption by onscientising the patriotic mind of Nigeria to protect the fabrics of Nigeria nationahood.It is recommended that the government should consciously reduce corruption in the system by strengthen the institutions and political structure in the country. The activities of the political class should be checkmate by the various levels of government that are put in palces for chack and balances.

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